

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

RISIS DATASET CIB2/CINNOB

WP5/WP8/WP9

OVERALL PROGRESS REPORT

REPORTING PERIOD 1 (January 2019 – June 2020)

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1. Introduction and overview

The Corporate Invention Board (CIB2) database is designed for the analysis of technological knowledge creation of the worldwide top corporate R&D performers, using patents of invention as a proxy. It includes 3992 companies. The list of companies was elaborated using the EU Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboards and the names of WIPO top applicants. CIB2 focuses on the priority patents applied by the parent companies and the subsidiaries they control. For patents, it relies on the patent data included in the RISIS Patent Database (RPD), another RISIS dataset derived from the PATSTAT 2017 April release from the European Patent Office. The coverage of the database is 2000-2015.

Besides the date of the filing and the office where the patent was first filed, we specifically consider in CIB2 core attributes of priority patents:

- **Their technological content using the standard technology classification and textual sources of information,**
- **The geographical location of inventive activities based on inventors addresses,**
- **The legal organisations that apply for patents (the applicants),**
- **Characteristics linked to the value of the patents.**

Overall 6,158,064 priority patents of inventions were applied for from 2000 to 2015. They include 15,712,409 inventors.

CIB2 also gives basic data of the companies (locations, sectors, size, financial data).

CIB2 database is a rich data source for research activities in the production of knowledge using patent data. It allows studying the dynamics of knowledge creation along different dimensions: space, actors and technologies. CIB2 database enables to access to these dimensions at a coarse level or at a fine grained level using either usual classification (for technologies, geography) or designing ad-hoc data subsets of patents for specific topics of inventions, for a particular type of institutions and/or in given geographical spaces.

Link to metadata in RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/2/metadata>

Link to documentation in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3733483#.XtiiiXZ4zaYU>

Link to tutorial in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3754791#.XtiiiXZ4zaYU>

2. Activities and Developments in the first reporting period

2.1. Maintenance

The release of the first version of the CIB2 database was planned during the first 18th month of RISIS2. Its first version of CIB2 (CIB2.v1.1) has been released in February 2020 (planned December 2019).

It provides the priority patents applied by the top R&D performer worldwide, based on data included in Risis Patent Database. It includes the priority patents applied by the parent companies and the subsidiaries they control (selected based on information available in the ORBIS database). In order to be constructed, CIB2 has required two sources of information: a fully developed Risis Patent Database (another dataset available in RISIS2) for the patent data and the list of the top corporate R&D performers worldwide (and their consolidated subsidiaries). Matching names of firms (parent company or subsidiaries) with the names of applicants of priority patents allows collecting the patents of CIB2. The matching phase comprises an automated matching phase based on similarity measurement of names and a manual checking phase. In order to improve the matching between the list of the company names with the names of the legal applicants (compared to what has been done for the construction of CIB1 in RISIS1), a new textual analysis tool has been designed at LISIS (UGE) between M6 and M14: the PAM system (Patent Approximation Matches system). It combines full text search techniques with several approximate string-matching algorithms and calculate its own PAM score.

CIB2 includes 6,158,064 priority patents of inventions applied by 3992 top corporate R&D performers headquartered worldwide. The coverage of the database is 2000-2015.

The CIB2 data are organised in a database using MySQL. The database is developed and maintained by UGE. The database is located on the servers of UGE at Marne La Vallee, France. Moreover, basic data on the companies (locations, sectors, size, financial data) were also included in CIB2. CIB2 and Firm_Reg were also linked. The CIB2 companies were included in Firm_Reg. A Firm_Reg_id was allocated to the parent companies.

The CIB2 documentation and tutorial were provided in March 2020.

During spring 2020, we have improved the CIB2.v1.1 version. It will enable to propose a CIB2.v1.2 version.

2.2. Deepening

The main development related to the top corporate R&D performers is to build a repository CInnoB (Corporate Innovation Board) providing indicators on corporate R&D and innovation activities at the consolidated firm level for the corporate R&D investors included in CIB2. It should include data describing the firms and gather data related to their innovative activities relying on the data available in the different data sources in RISIS2. It aims to include in aggregated data on corporate patents, scientific publications, trademarks, participations to FPs and a set of more general information on the firms (sector, locations, financial data). It will provide indicators allowing the study of the firms activities according to several dimensions: time, technologies, scientific domains, geographical location of the R&D activities, collaborations.

The definition and preliminary elaboration of the CINNOB data model including the definition of the list of indicators for firm geography, financial data and patents was planned in spring 2020. They are still in progress.

In December 2019, the general data related to the firms (sector, location, financial data) were extracted from the Orbis database and uploaded in a Mysql database at UGE.

In February 2020, UGE has started to work on the delineation of the scientific publications of 628 CIB2 companies in the sectors of chemicals, pharmaceuticals and biotechnologies in the CWTS publication database. A large set of candidate names of institutions signing scientific publications was provided by CWTS and UGE is currently matching these names with firms names (parent companies and their subsidiaries).

2.3. Access and usages

CIB2 has been recently released (just before the pandemic Covid) and the database has not been extensively used until now.

CIB2 was presented in February 2020 at a meeting of the French Club Patent Analytics taking place at OST in Paris.

Two visits (one on-site, one on-line) were organised (on a beta version of CIB2) in 2019 and 2020. They both aim at identifying the top corporate actors in the fields or aerospace either for further network analysis or innovation management in this field.

Preliminary research is currently taking place at UGE to analyse the geography of the inventive activities of the CIB2 top worldwide companies at the fine grain level (Urban and Rural Areas). Examples of the geography of the inventive activities based on inventors' addresses in CIB2 firms (triadic patents; period of time 2011-2014) are shown below (Overall locations of inventions in worldwide Urban Rural Areas and a focus on the inventions in European Urban Rural Areas).

CIB2 companies were linked to Firm_Reg and were given a Firm_Reg_id.

- ▶ CIB2 link to metadata in RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/2/metadata>
- ▶ CIB2 link to documentation in Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/record/3733483#.XtiiXZ4zaYU>
- ▶ CIB2 link to tutorial in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/3754791#.XtihiZ4zaYU>

3. Outlook and next steps

A CIB2.v1.2 should be released at M21. It will include a set of patents from Risis Patent Database that have been misallocated and discarded from CIB2.v1.1 (false negative). Compared to CIB.v1.1, CIB2.v1.2 should include around 10% of additional patents (most often from Asian firms).

Then a second version of CIB2 should be made available in spring 2022. It will be based on a new Risis patent Database version (See below 6.Risis Patent Database).

A first version of the CINNOB database will be released at M24. In addition to a set of information on the companies, it will provide a list of patent indicators at the firm level to characterise the corporate technological activities.

Adding in CINNOB indicators that will be calculated using data from other RISIS database will be done after M24 according to their availability. We aim at providing indicators of the corporate activities using data extracted from EUPRO (AIT), the database of design (ISI-Fraunhofer) and CWTS Publication database (partial coverage related to some industrial sectors).

Integration in the RCF depends on RCF developments. It is accepted that CIB2/CINNOB will be a test for integration.

4. List of milestones and Deliverables (WP5, WP9)

D5.1 - Work plan on Maintenance CIB2 (October 2019).

D5.2 - First interim report on Maintenance of RISIS core dataset (June 2020) Contribution to the report.

D9.1 - Consolidated work plan on datasets development CIB2/CINNOB (December 2019).

The CIB2 documentation was provided and uploaded in Zenodo in March 2020.

The CIB2 tutorial was provided and uploaded in Zenodo in March 2020.

The CIB documentation was uploaded in HAL, the French Open Archive Repository (hal-02518301).

5. List of accesses

Applicant	Applicant institution	Project Title	Date
Robert Magnuszewski	Universite Roma1	European Aerospace Industry Network Analysis	25.03.2019
Denisa Naidin	Toulouse Business	Innovation management in the space sector	29.01.2020

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